

Obtaining Information Beyond Speech Technologies for a User-Adaptive Multimodal Dialogue System

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Abstract

In this article we consider our plans to improve an already implemented multimodal dialogue system for control of appliances in an ambient intelligent environment, called *Mayordomo*. We think that by means of the planned improvements, the dialogue system will become more user-adaptive and thus the interaction will be more user-friendly. The adaptation will be implemented considering information not taken into account in the original version of the system, specifically user localization and identification. The paper discusses our recent research on methods to achieve this sort of information, as well as our plans to make use of user profiles.

Pridobivanje neverbalnih informacij v večmodalnem sistemu za dialog, sposobnem prilagoditve uporabniku

Prispevek obravnava naše načrte za nadaljnje delo pri izboljšavi delujočega sistema za večmodalni dialog *Mayordomo*, ki je namenjen krmiljenju naprav v okolju ambientalne inteligence. Predvidevamo, da bodo opisane izboljšave sistem še bolj približale uporabniku. Pri implementaciji izboljšane verzije bomo dodatno upoštevali predvsem informacijo o identiteti ter lokaciji uporabnika, kar v prvotni različici sistema ni bilo upoštevano. V prispevku opisujemo postopke, s katerimi pridobivamo opisane nove podatke, ter načrte za izdelavo uporabniških profilov.

1. Introduction

This multimodal dialogue system employed for the elaboration is *Mayordomo* (Ábalos et al., 2010). The aim of *Mayordomo* is to centralize control of appliances in a home. The interaction with appliance can be through spontaneous speech or through a traditional GUI interface, based on keyboard and mouse.

Besides handling appliance, the system support different types of users, depending on the administrator level and the experience with *Mayordomo*. The system administrator has privileges to perform special actions, for example, installing and uninstalling appliances. Also, restrictions are allowed to some users. For instance, parents can forbid that children watch TV after 10 p.m. The system creates a log of all actions carried out within the environment by any user.

In this article we purpose an upgrade of *Mayordomo* by making it user-adaptive. So, the user can be located and identified by the system in an implicit way, being not necessary saying where the user is, ridding him off about providing unnecessary information. This information about the user can be used to optimize the dialogue with the user.

The paper is organized as follows. First, some methods are presented for automatically locating and recognizing the user such as RFIDs, cameras, and microphone arrays. In section 2 we explain the user-adaptive dialogue system. Finally, section 3 presents the conclusions and outlines possibilities for future work.

2. Methods to locate and recognize the user with *Mayordomo*

Using *Mayordomo*, the localization and identity of the user can be deduced using different ways to extract information, or even using all these ways together. In this section we describe three of the most common ways: radio frequency identification (RFID), cameras and microphone arrays. Using these devices, the user is not required to say where and who he is as the system can get this information automatically.

2.1. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID)

RFIDs are considered one of the main ways for physical browsing, which is an interaction paradigm that associates digital information with physical objects (Aghajan et al., 2010). The interaction takes place using mobile terminals, such a mobile phones or cards that have one tag associated with a reader device. Each tag contains a universal resource identifier (URI, or Web address). The readers are distributed throughout the environment. Each RFID reader has a serial or identification number. When one of the tagged objects is scanned by the reader, the tag and the identification number of the reader are sent to the dialogue system. The distance between the physical object and the RFID reader can range from a centimetre to four meters. Usually, in closed and small environments this distance is not very large.

To be useful for our purposes, the dialogue system must know who is the user carrying each tag. Taking into account this information, the system can find out which was the last RFID reader used by the user, and thus deduce his localization.

RFID devices have been used in several research projects concerned with user localization. For example, López-Cózar et al. (2006) used RFID devices to locate students in an educational environment, whereas Haya et al. (2004) employed these devices in a home environment.

2.2. Cameras

In addition to provide information about user localization, cameras can help in detecting whether the user is talking or not, for example, using lip-motion information (Hazen et al., 2003).

Using cameras, the user can be identified by recognizing his face. This process can be carried out in two stages: face detection and face recognition. In the first stage the face is localized in the sequence of images provided by the camera. Many approaches can be used for this task, and many solutions already exist. One of them, which is used by *Mayordomo*, is based on the open source computer vision library *openCV*. This face detector implements a version of the face detection technique, first developed by Paul Viola and Michael Jones, which is commonly known as the Viola-Jones detector (Bradski & Kaehler, 2008). This technique was later extended by Rainer Lienhart and Jochen Maydt. The detector uses Haar-like wavelets created by adding and subtracting rectangular image regions, and then thresholding the result.

After the face of the user has been detected and extracted from the sequence of images, we must carry out face recognition. A commonly used method for doing this is by using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Albiol et al., 2005). Using this method, the feature vector that represents the face, is calculated from an individual face image and then a decision is made regarding the candidate face, for example, using a number of classifiers. A weakness of this camera approach is that the user's face might not be visible for the camera as it can be hidden by other objects.

2.3. Microphone arrays

A microphone array consists of multiple microphones placed at different spatial locations. Microphone arrays have been often used to solve, or at least reduce, the effects of the so called *cocktail party* problem. These arrays are very apparent for hands-free speech recognition applications, such as *Mayordomo*, in which it is not possible to use a close-talking microphone (Cherry, 1953). For example, Brandstein et al. (1997) used a linear intersection and employed sensor array time-delay estimate information. Also, Sturim et al. (1997) implemented the tracking of multiple talkers using this type of array.

As the input to the microphone array is the user's voice, which is specific for each person, these arrays can be useful as well to identify the speaker. The process of doing this is called *automatic speaker recognition* (Reynolds & Rose, 1995). As with any other automatic recognition process, speaker recognition consists of two stages: feature extraction and classification. The aim of feature extraction is to remove unnecessary information from the sensor data, and convert the properties of the

signal which are important for pattern recognition to a format that simplifies the distinction of the classes. Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) are normally used as features, whereas Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) is the most common method for classification.

Speaker recognition can be *text dependent* or *text independent*. The difference is that in the first type the meaning of the text is employed for the recognition task, whereas it is not used in the second type. The second type is more convenient for our system and thus the one that we will use.

High level features can also be used for text independent speaker recognition, such as word idiolect, pronunciation, phone usage and prosody. However, as we have observed that with *Mayordomo* the dialogues are very short, we think these features are not very appropriate.

2.4. Combining different approaches

Face recognition and automatic speaker recognition share a potential drawback, namely, they can be unreliable due to distortions. In the case of speaker recognition, distortion is normally caused by background noise, whereas in the case of face recognition it is caused by changes in lighting and in the user's appearance. In order to make the process of user identification more reliable, combining both methods is possible and has already been investigated (Albiol et al., 2005). In order to get the best performance possible, we plan to make *Mayordomo* combine the methods discussed above, and decide about the user's localization and identity on the basis of the combined data.

3. Information management for user-adaptive dialogue

In this section we describe how we plan to use the information about user identification in *Mayordomo* in order to enable a more user-friendly interaction.

3.1. Input information about user identification

Once we know who is the current user, we can adapt the system's performance. To do this, the first step will be designing a user model. Taking into account (Webb et al., 2001), the four main issues to describe are:

- (1) the cognitive processes that underlie the user's actions (*behaviour*);
- (2) the differences between the user's skills and expert's skills (degree of *expertise*);
- (3) the user's behavioural patterns or *preferences*; and
- (4) the user's *characteristics*.

In our case, the user model will be based on a number of parameters used to adapt the dialogue system, for example age, previous experience using the system, user preferences, interaction language, etc. These parameters will be stored in a *user profile*.

The user profile for a new user can be built either *manually*, in which case a system developer just fills in all the information that he knows about each user, or *automatically*, in which case the system prompts the user for his/her personal data and for general information (e.g.,

name, age, language, gender, etc.). This second approach was used by Lucas et al. (2009) to develop user profiles for a dialogue system that controls a Hi-Fi device.

The management of all the information stored in the user profiles will be carried out by a *Profile Manager*, which will interact with some modules in the dialogue system, for example, the Dialogue Manager.

Table 1 shows an excerpt of a user profile to be created for our system. It represents a profile filled in by a bilingual woman called Mary, who is twenty-five years old. She prefers speech-based system's interaction in English, although she wants to read the text in the graphical interface (user interface) in Spanish. She is a system administrator and thus is allowed to use all the appliances in the house (in this example, lights and TV). Besides, when Mary is at home, she normally watches channel number six on TV and likes a lightning ambient created by all the lights in the living room at medium brightness. Finally, she prefers speech for the input interaction to the system and the graphical interface for the output (the system does not interact with her using speech).

General user information	
Name	Mary
Genre	Female
Age	25
Language preferences (used by the system)	
ASR	English
UI	Spanish
TTS	English
Characteristics	
Level	Administrator (3)
Privileges	Light – Allowed
	TV – Allowed
User preferences	
Light	Medium brightness
TV	Channel 6
Interaction user-system	
Input	Speech
Output	Graphical interface

Table 1. Example of user profile

Our system's implementation follows the definition of *sessions* and *dialogue turns* presented in Pargellis et al. (2004). *Mayordomo* will control the interaction with the user by means of a set of dialogues which start with an activation command and finish with a close command. A dialogue is a sequence of turns, i.e. interactions in which either the user or the system say something.

In the following sections, we explain some parameters of our user profiles.

3.2. Age

Generally, the dialogue systems which adapt their performance to older or younger users create ranges of age for the users. For example, in Georgila et al. (2008) older participants were aged between 50 and 85, whereas younger participants were aged 20 to 30.

Wolters et al.' (2009) group studied what would happen if the relevant user groups were not delineated by age but by characteristic patterns of behaviour. They analysed whether users can be grouped according to the way in which they interact with the system. The statistical analysis methodology that they used allows identifying "extreme" users and "typical" users, without using age in the initial analysis. They quantified the *interaction style* (the linguistic choices that users make) of each user based on a linguistic analysis of their dialogues. Examples of relevant linguistic choices are choosing between different expressions of agreement (e.g., "yes" against "that's fine"), or using politeness expressions like "please". Finally, they have shown that being old does not necessarily mean acting old. Even though older users were more likely to have a "social" interaction style than younger users, a sizeable proportion of older users preferred the same "factual" interaction style as younger users.

For the implementation of the *Mayordomo* system, we have chosen the common approach of creating ranges of age for users, as done by Georgila et al. (2008). Our analysis is made in two levels: lexical and concerned with dialogue acts. Similarly as Wolters et al. (2009), Georgila et al. (2008) argued that older users produce longer dialogues than younger users. They also have a richer vocabulary and use a larger variety of speech acts. Besides, younger users tend to restrict themselves to speech acts that are of immediate relevance to the task. A third of all words uttered by younger users are "yes" or "no", despite 13% for older users. In order to express approval or disapproval, older users are more likely to use expressions other than "yes", such as "fine". Also, they are more likely to use expressions that are more appropriate in human/human interactions, such as forms of "goodbye" or "thank you". Moreover, Georgila et al. (2008) compared their study with the word-level analyses of the MeMo corpus of G6dde et al. (2008), and concluded that the social interaction words that distinguish between older and younger users appear to be task-specific.

Table 2 shows an example of interaction between two users and *Mayordomo*. As said above, Mary is a 25 years old woman, whereas Damien is a 65 years old man. The example shows that *Mayordomo* adapts the dialogue depending on the age of the user, creating more complex and polite dialogues in the second case.

<i>Younger user (Mary)</i>	<i>Older user (Damien)</i>
S: Hi Mary!	S: Welcome Damien.
U: Hi Mayordomo. Please switch on the lights.	U: Good morning. Please switch on the lights.
S: Where?	S: Excuse me, where do you want me to switch on the lights?
U: In the living room.	U: In the living room, please.
S: Done.	S: The lights in the living room are now turned on.
	U: Thank you.

Table 2. Example of dialogue adaptation by age

3.3. Preferences

Lucas et al. (2009) proposed to implement systems' adaptation taking into account a number of *usage statistics*, which are divided in different groups according to domain-knowledge. This enables the system to infer the preferences for each user among the different statistic groups, and among the different items belonging to the same group. To sum up, the statistic counts are used to build a model for user preferences, which allows the system to suggest hypotheses in incomplete information

situations. When in a system-user interaction the dialogue manager finds that there is lack of information, instead of directly asking the user, the system must look first into the user profile in order to decide whether the user has a clear preference for a certain action.

Table 3 shows two sample expected interactions with *Mayordomo*. The first one will consider stored usage statistics, whereas the second will not. *Mayordomo* will adapt the dialogue depending on the stored usage information, asking for more information in the second case.

Using stored information	Not using stored information
S: Hi Mary.	S: Hi Mary.
U: Switch on the TV	U: Switch on the TV
S: Done.	S: Done.
Note: the system statistics about the user show that Mary prefers channel six and loud TV volume.	U: Please select channel six.
	S: Done.
	U: Turn up the volume.
	S: Done.

Table 3. Example of dialogue adaptation by preferences

3.4. Characteristics (privileges)

Another important issue in our system is in terms of usage permissions (*user privileges*). *Mayordomo* stores information related to user-appliance interaction with a tag regarding user permission for each appliance. If the interaction is not allowed, *Mayordomo* informs the user, as can be observed in **Table 4**.

3.5. Management (degree of expertise)

Mayordomo enables different kinds of user depending on the number of times they have used the system. For example, **Table 4** shows that Mary is a novice user because it is the first time that she interacts with the system. Instead, Peter is an expert user because he has used it many times and knows perfectly how to use it. By modifying the behaviour of the Dialogue Manager and the output of the Natural Response Generator module, the system avoids giving basic information to expert users in order to avoid boring them with already known information.

4. Conclusions and future work

In this paper we have described some methods to obtain extra information from the user of *Mayordomo*, a multimodal dialogue system used in home environments.

This information goes beyond the strict orders or queries that can be done through dialogue. The extra-information can be divided into two groups: location and identity.

The location refers the exactly point or room where the user is. This location can be deduced using RFIDs, cameras or microphone arrays; or even, by combining of all.

The second group, identity information, deals with the different characteristics of users. The goal is to provide better adapted information depending on some characteristics, such as age, preferences, privileges and degree of expertise.

As future work we plan one evaluation of the different methods to obtaining information, as well as a comparative between all of them, with particular attention in how the information is received and adapted. Also, users will answer some questionnaires with the aim of compare the adaptation results with the true preferences and likes.

<i>Novice / basic user</i>	<i>Expert user</i>
S: Hi Rose.	S: Hi Peter
U: Which appliances are there in the hall?	U: Switch on the light.
S: There are two lights (ceiling light and lamp) and piped music.	S: Which light?
U: Please switch on the light.	U: The ceiling light.
S: Sorry, which light? The ceiling light or the lamp?	S: You are not allowed to do this.
U: The ceiling light.	
S: You are not allowed to use the ceiling light. Please contact the system administrator to get assistance.	

Table 4. *Examples of dialogue adaptation by degree of expertise*

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